

Regarding the fast moving Muons - Conclusions that disagree with Relativity

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Abstract.

Most scientists believe there are a lot of proofs that the special theory of relativity is correct. According to them, one of the proofs is the dilation of time on the fast moving muons that are produced by cosmic rays in the atmosphere of the Earth.

On this paper, I will show that the idea that there is dilation of time on the fast moving muons that are produced in the atmosphere of the Earth, is wrong!!!

In fact, the whole approach to this subject by the scientific community is wrong!

Regarding the motion of the muons that are moving towards the humans on the Earth, what we have is not just motion of the muons on the reference frame of the humans!

Instead, what we also have is motion of the humans on the reference frame of the muons, meaning that we have two reference frames in relative motion with each other, and of course we must say that **there is no preferred reference frame!**

The muons, regarding themselves as stationary!!!

For the muons, the humans(and the Earth) are the ones that are on the move!

But as you will see, if we apply the way of thinking of the scientific community, **there is no reciprocity regarding time and length!**

The time and the distance on the one reference frame are smaller than the other!

Why this is happening since there is no preferred reference frame?

Why is not happening the opposite?

Something is wrong in the way that the scientific community interprets the findings!!!

Introduction.

Most scientists believe there are a lot of proofs that the special theory of relativity is correct. According to them, one of the proofs is the dilation of time on the fast moving muons that are produced by cosmic rays in the atmosphere of the Earth.

Also, most of the others so-called proofs, are based on the decay of elementary particles, which means that are based on the same way of thinking that involves the fast moving muons!

My opinion is that the whole approach to this subject by the scientific community is wrong!

So, **next we will see if there are any problems with these ideas!**

At first, I will present the findings of a famous experiment regarding the motion of the muons, and also I will present the way of thinking of the scientific community.

Afterwards we will see some examples regarding the distances on a reference frame that will be extremely helpful in our attempt to understand the problem.

Finally, we will focus on what happens regarding the motion of the muons, and why the interpretation of the findings by the scientific community is wrong!!!

First, let's see some things regarding the fast moving muons.

When cosmic rays (extremely fast moving protons) strike the atmosphere of the Earth, **muons** are produced, and those muons are moving towards the surface of the Earth at a velocity near the speed of light.

Scientists David Frisch and James Smith placed a detector at the top of Mount Washington and they detected about 565 muons per hour.

This means that if we place the detector around the Earth at an altitude similar with the top the Mount Washington, the detector will detect about 565 **muons** per hour.

Using the same detector in Cambridge, Massachusetts they detected about 410 muons per hour.

This means that if we place the detector around the Earth at an altitude similar with the Cambridge, Massachusetts, the detector will detect about 410 **muons** per hour.

But, 410 muons per hour is much more than what they expected to find!!!

Muons at rest relative to the Earth, have a mean lifetime of 2.2 microseconds(μs), and a half-life of 1.56 microseconds(μs) (i've found the numbers on the internet, I hope are right).

Due to the fact that the half-life of the muons is 1,56 microseconds, the scientists expected to detect about 30 muons per hour in Cambridge, Massachusetts, but they found 410 muons per hour!!!!!!

The scientific community says that this is happening because time dilation and length contraction occurs!!!

The difference in altitude between the top of the Mount Washington and the Cambridge, Massachusetts, where the experiments were conducted, is about 1905 metres.

From sea level, the height of the Mount Washington is 1917 metres.

{ What we care about is the difference in altitude between the locations where the experiments were conducted, which is 1905 metres, and we don't care about the actual height of the Mount Washington from sea level.

From now on for convenience reasons and to make the examples simpler and more understandable, when I say "sea level" I will actually mean an altitude similar with the altitude at Cambridge, Massachusetts where the experiment was conducted, which is a few metres(12 metres) above sea level.

As I have said, what we focus on is the the difference in altitude between the locations where the experiments were conducted, which is 1905 metres. }

The average speed of the **muons** that are moving from the top of the Mount Washington towards the surface of the Earth, is approximately 0.993 c .

(The muons speed at sea level, is slightly slower than the speed at the top of the Mountain.)

The muons that have a speed 0.993 c , will travel the distance of 1905 metres in about 6.4 microseconds(μs), according to a clock on Earth.

According to the scientific community, the time dilation factor for the relative speed(which is 0.993 c) between the Earth and the muons is approximately **8.8**.

So, according to the scientific community, for the muons only 0,73 microseconds($6.4/8.8=0.73 \mu\text{s}$) have past while they are moving from an altitude similar with the top of the Mount Washington towards the sea level.

Also, there is length contraction on the reference frame of the muons, meaning that the distance for the muons is 217 metres($1905/8.8=217$ metres), and not 1905 metres(figures A & B)!!!

As I have said earlier the half-life of the muons is 1.56 microseconds(μs), and because for the muons only 0.73 microseconds(μs) have past while they are moving from an altitude similar with the top of the Mount Washington to Cambridge, Massachusetts, that's why they are so many of them at sea level!!!

The **Earth** and the **muons** agree on which is the relative speed between them.

The Earth "says" that on its own reference frame the distance between the muons and the surface of the Earth was 1905 metres, and after 6.4 microseconds the muons have reached the surface of the Earth(Cambridge, Massachusetts), and the muons are "saying" that on their own reference frame the distance between the surface of the Earth and the muons was 217 metres, and after 0.73 microseconds the muons have reached the surface of the Earth !!!!!

Therefore, the **Earth** and the **muons** agree that their relative speed is approximately 297.5 metres per microsecond, or 0.993 c !!!!

To understand what the scientific community says let's see the figures A & B.

On the **figures A & B** i have changed the shape of the Mount Washington and I use a right-angled triangle as the shape of the Mount Washington.

I did that in order to have a straight vertical line from the top to the base of the mountain, and with this configuration we have the muons moving next to the mountain from the top to the base, which is something that will help us understand the relative motion between the muons and the mountain.

(On the figures A & B where I write "sea level" I mean Cambridge, Massachusetts where the experiment was conducted, as I have explain earlier.)

Figure B. The muon A is now next to the human B.

At the top of the mountain there is the human A and down at the base of the mountain(sea level) there is the human B(**figures A & B**).

Imagine that a muon, the muon A, is moving towards the surface of the Earth and it passes next to the human A which is at the top of the Mount Washington, as we see in the **figure A**.

When the muon A passes next to the human A, on the reference frame of the human A, the human B is 1905 metres away, but according to the scientific community on the reference frame of the muon A the human B is 217 metres away(**figure A**)!!!

Also according to the scientific community, the internal clock of the muon A will count 0.73 microseconds while it is moving from the human A to the human B(**figure B**).

Of course, the muon A "thinks" for itself that it is stationary, and the reality for the muon A is that the humans the mountain and the Earth are on the move, meaning that the muon A actually "thinks" that the human B travels 217 metres in 0.73 microseconds!!!

The human B says that the muon A is moving from the human A(**figure A**)to the human B (**figure B**) in 6.4 microseconds(μ s).

-Next, we will see some examples regarding the distances on a reference frame that will be extremely helpful in our attempt to understand the problem.-

Suppose that somewhere(anywhere) there are two humans, the human A and the human B, that are stationary relative to each other(**figure 1**).

We will say that these two humans are on the same reference frame, because they are stationary relative to each other.

Suppose that according to the two humans the distance between them is 1000 metres(**figure 1**). If we want to talk about how far away from the human A is the human B, we will say that "on the reference frame of the human A, the human B is 1000 metres away".

Now let's add something to the **figure 1** example.

Suppose that next to the human B there is a car and a muon(**figure 2**), and both the car and the muon are on the move relative to the humans A & B, with the difference being that the muon is moving away from the human A and the car is moving towards the human A.

If we want to talk about the distance between the human A and the car or the muon on the reference frame of the human A, we will say that "on the reference frame of the human A the car and the muon are 1000 metres away"!!!

Why we will say that???

We will say this because the car and the muon are next to the human B who is stationary relative to the human A(**figure 2**), and according to the human A the human B is 1000 metres away, meaning that **everything that is next to the human B, regardless of its motion, is 1000 metres away form the human A** on the reference frame of the human A!!!

Now imagine a little different scenario.

Suppose that there is the human A that considers himself as stationary and a muon is moving away from the human A(**figure 3**).

If we say that at a specific moment, on the reference frame of the human A the distance between him and the muon is 500 metres(**figure 3**), what do we mean by that???

We mean that if there was the human B, for example, next to the muon (as we see in the **figure 4**) and the human B was stationary relative to the human A, the distance between the two humans on their reference frame would be 500 metres!!!

As we see on the **figure 4**, the reason why we say that at a specific moment, on the reference frame of the human A the muon is 500 metres away from the human A is because the muon

is next to the human B which is stationary relative to the human A, and on the reference frame of the human A the distance between the two humans is 500 metres!!!

Figure 4. The human B is stationary relative to the human A.

Of course what we have seen on the previous examples applies also for the muons and not only for the humans.
Let's see the next examples.

Suppose there are two muons, the muons A & B, which are stationary relative to each other(**figure 5**).

We will say that these two muons are on the same reference frame, because they are stationary relative to each other.

Suppose that according to the two muons the distance between them is 1000 metres(**figure 5**).
If we want to talk about how far away from the muon A is the muon B, we will say that "on the reference frame of the muon A, the muon B is 1000 metres away".

Now let's add something to the **figure 5** example.

Suppose that next to the muon B there is a car and a human(**figure 6**), and both the car and the human are on the move relative to the muons A & B, with the difference being that the human is moving away from the muon A and the car is moving towards the muon A.

If we want to talk about the distance between the muon A and the car or the human on the reference frame of the muon A, we will say that "on the reference frame of the muon A the car and the human are 1000 metres away"!!!

Why we will say that???

We will say this because the car and the human are next to the muon B which is stationary relative to the muon A(**figure 6**), and according to the muon A the muon B is 1000 metres away, meaning that **everything that is next to the muon B, regardless of its motion**, is 1000 metres away from the muon A on the reference frame of the muon A!!!

Now imagine a little different scenario.

Suppose that there is the muon A that considers itself as stationary and a human is moving away from the muon A (**figure 7**).

If we say that at a specific moment, on the reference frame of the muon A the distance between the muon A and the human is 200 metres (**figure 7**), what do we mean by that???

We mean that if there was the muon B, for example, next to the human (as we see in the **figure 8**) and the muon B was stationary relative to the muon A, the distance between the two muons on their reference frame would be 200 metres!!!

As we see on the **figure 8**, the reason why we say that at a specific moment, on the reference frame of the muon A the human is 200 metres away from the muon A is because the human is next to the muon B which is stationary relative to the muon A, and on the reference frame of the muon A the distance between the two muons is 200 metres!!!

Figure 8. The muon B is stationary relative to the muon A.

What we have seen on the previous examples is extremely important and we will need it for the next examples where we will see again the motion of the fast moving muons while moving towards the surface of the Earth.

Let's see the **figure 9**, which is the same with the **figure A**.

As I've said earlier about the **figure A**, on the **figure 9** (and also on the next figures) I've changed the shape of the Mount Washington and I use a right-angled triangle as the shape of the Mount Washington.

I did that in order to have a straight vertical line from the top to the base of the mountain, and with this configuration we have the muons moving next to the mountain from the top to the base, which is something that will help us understand the relative motion between the muons and the mountain.

(On the figures, where I write "sea level" I mean an altitude similar with the Cambridge, Massachusetts where the experiment was conducted, as I have explain earlier.

What we care about is the difference in altitude between Cambridge, Massachusetts and the top of the Mount Washington where the two experiments were conducted, which is 1905 metres.)

At the top of the mountain there is the human A and down at the base of the mountain(sea level) there is the human B(**figure 9**).

Imagine that a muon, the muon A, is moving towards the surface of the Earth and it passes next to the human A which is at the top of the Mount Washington, as we see in the **figure 9**.

On the reference frame of the human A the human B is 1905 metres away, **but according to the scientific community**, when the muon A is next to the human A, on the reference frame of the muon A the human B is 217 metres away(**figure 9**)!!!

Question:

Is the muon A alone on its own reference frame???

Answer: No, it is not alone(**figure 10-A**), there are many other muons stationary relative to the muon A meaning that they are on the same reference frame!!

According to the scientific community, when the muon A is next to the human A, the muon A "says" that on its own reference frame the human B is 217 metres away from it, but the human B disagrees and says that on his own reference frame the muon A is 1905 metres away from him!!!

Both the human B and the muon A are talking about the distance between them, each on its own reference frame, but they disagree on which is that distance(**figure 9**)!!!

So, there is no reciprocity, but reciprocity is fundamental in special relativity, so how can this be happening!!!!!

Some may say that what we have here is the motion of a muon on the reference frame of the humans, and so there is no problem, but they are wrong!!!

What we have here is not the motion of muons on the reference frame of the humans, but instead there are two reference frames in relative motion with each other!!!

There is the reference frame of the humans and the reference frame of the muons(**figure 10-A**)

So, the muon A is not alone on its own reference frame!!!

While the muon A is moving towards the surface of the Earth, many other muons are making the same motion towards the surface of the Earth (**figure 10-A**), meaning that the muon A and all the other muons (**figure 10-A**) that are moving towards the surface of the Earth are stationary relative to each other which means that they are on the same reference frame!!!!

All these muons regard themselves as stationary meaning that they are in an inertial frame, and for them the reality is that the humans, the mountain and the Earth are actually those that are on the move!!!

(We don't actually need the Earth on the picture and so from now on we will talk only for the humans A & B and the mountain.

Actually, we also don't need the Mount Washington.

We only need the humans A & B.)

So, at the moment that the muon A is next to the human A at the top of the Mount Washington, there are thousands of muons that are between the muon A and the human B, and a muon is next to the human B at the base of the mountain (**figure 10-A**)!!!

The muon which is next to the human B let's call it muon B.

(Maybe there are more than one muons next to the human B, but let's say that in our case there is only one.)

All these muons(**figure 10-A**) are stationary relative to each other meaning they are on the same reference frame, and consider themselves as **being in an inertial reference frame!!!**

This means that what we have is two inertial reference frames in relative motion, the reference frame of the humans(with the mountain) and the reference frame of the muons(**figure 10-A**)!!!

When the muon A is next to the human A at the top of the mountain, there are many muons at a lower altitude than the muon A(also there are many muons at higher altitude), and there is a muon which is next to the human B which we call it muon B(**figure 10-A**).

The muon B is stationary relative to the muon A meaning they are on the same reference frame, and the human B is stationary relative to the human A.

So the question is:

Which is the distance between the muon A and the muon B(figure 10-A**) according to the muon A, meaning on the reference frame of the muons???**

The scientific community believes that when the muon A is next to the human A, on the reference frame of the muon A the human B is 217 metres away from it(**figure 9**)!!!

The muons regard themselves as stationary and they are saying that the humans are on the move.

When the muon A is next to the human A, the muon A says that the human B is on the move and he is next to the muon B which is stationary(**figure 10-A**)!!!

So, if we accept as reality what the scientific community believes, we can say that **the reason why the muon A says that on its own reference frame the human B is 217 metres away it's because he is next to the muon B(**figure 10-B**)**, which is similar with what we say for the humans where the human B says that on his own reference frame the muon A is 1905 metres away because the muon A is next to the human A(**figure 9**)!!!

So, if we accept what the scientific community is saying, this means that **on the reference frame of the muons the distance between the muons A & B is 217 metres(**figure 10-B**)**, and when the muon A is next to the human A on the reference frame of the muon A the human B is 217 metres away from it because he is next to the muon B!!!

The muons A & B are stationary relative to each other, and if the distance between them is 217 metres on their reference frame, this means that for the muon A everything that is next to the muon B is 217 metres away, and so the human B which is next to the muon B is 217 metres away from the muon A at the moment when muon A and human A are next to each other!!!

If, hypothetically, according to the muons the distance between the muons A & B was 500 metres, in that case everything that is next to the muon B would be 500 metres away from the muon A on the reference frame of the muon A, meaning that in this case the human B would be 500 metres away from the muon A on the reference frame of the muon A.

Which is the reason why the the human B says that the muon A is 1905 metres away(**figure 9**). The reason is the fact that the muon A is next to the human A, because for the human B everything that is next to the human A is 1905 metres away from him(**figure 9**).

Applying the same way of thinking, if we say that according to the muon A the human B is 217 metres away from it, this is happening because the human B is next to the muon B(**figure 10-B**), and so we must say that on the reference frame of the muons A & B the distance between them is 217 metres, and everything that is next to the muon B is 217 metres away from the muon A on the reference frame of the muons!!!

(Again I have to remind you that the reality for the muons is that the humans and the mountain are moving.)

See again the examples with the **figures 1-2-3-4-5-6-7-8** in order to understand why i'm saying all this!!!

Figure 10-A. According to the muons, the humans and the mountain are those that are on the move.

The muon A regards the muon B as stationary relative to it, as the human B regards the human A as stationary relative to him.

What do we have here?

We have the scientific community saying that **when the muon A is next to the human A at the top of the mountain, on the reference frame of the muon A the distance between the muon A and the human B is 217 metres (figure 9).**

To help you with the problem, here is the question that you have to answer:

When the muon A is next to the human A, which is the distance between the muon A and the muon B (figures 10-A, 10-B) on the reference frame of the muons???

If you answer that the distance between the muons A & B on their reference frame is 217 metres, in that case you can say that when the human B is next to the muon B he is 217 metres away from the muon A on the reference frame of the muon A!!!

But if you give a different answer you cannot say that the human B is 217 metres away from the muon A on the reference frame of the muon A when he is next to the muon B!!!

Can we answer, for example, that the distance between the muons A & B on the reference frame of the muons is 1905 metres, or 1000 metres, or 500 metres, or 100 metres, or something else???

Think about it!!!

According to the scientific community, when the muon A and the human A are next to each other (figures 9, 10-A, 10-B) the muon A "says":

- "On my reference frame the human B is 217 metres away."

So the question is:

At this moment how far away is the muon B according to the muon A???

What we have is **not** the motion of the muon A on the reference frame of the humans!!!

What we have is relative motion between two reference frames, the reference frame of the muons and the reference frame of the humans!!!

There is motion of the muons on the reference frame of the humans, and motion of the humans on the reference frame of the muons.

The muons are "saying" that the humans are on the move with a direction from the muon B towards the muon A!!!

So, the reality for the muons is that the humans A & B are on the move, therefore, if we say that at the moment the muon A is next to the human A, on the reference frame of the muon A the human B is 217 metres away, the reason for saying this is because while the human B is moving towards the muons B & A, when he passes next to the muon B (figure 10-B) he is 217 metres away from the muon A on the reference frame of the muons, because the muon B is on the same reference frame with the muon A and the distance between the two muons on their reference frame is 217 metres!!!!

Why am i saying all this???

Because the scientific community says that when the muon A is next to the human A on the top of the mountain (figure 9), on the reference frame of the muon A the human B is 217 metres away from the muon A, even though on the reference frame of the human A the human B is 1905 metres away!!!!

So, if we accept this thing that the scientific community says, we must say that on the reference frame of the muons the distance between the muons A & B is 217 metres (**figure 10-B**), and whatever passes next to the muon B, like for example the human B, it is also 217 metres away from the muon A on the reference frame of the muon A!!!

See again the examples with the **figures 1-2-3-4-5-6-7-8** in order to understand why i'm saying all this!!!

So, there are many muons that are moving towards the Earth, meaning that when the muon A is next to the human A, another muon, which we call muon B, is next to the human B. (**figures 10-A, 10-B, 11**).

What is the reality for the human B???

The human B says:

- "When the muon B is next to me the muon A is next to the human A, and that's why at this moment the muon A is 1905 metres away from me" (**figure 11**).

But the muon A "says":

- "When the human A is next to me the human B is next to the muon B, and that's why at this moment the human B is 217 metres away from me" (**figure 11**).

Therefore, both the human B and the muon A are talking about the distance between them at the moment when human A & muon A are next to each other and also human B & muon B are next to each other, meaning that they are talking about the distance between them referring to the same moment, but they disagree on which is that distance because the human B says that the distance between them is 1905 metres but the muon A says that the distance between them is 217 metres!!!

Why am I saying that the human B and the muon A refer to the same moment talking about the distance between them???

They refer to the same moment because both they refer to the moment when human A & muon A are next to each other and also human B & muon B are next to each other!!!

So, there is no reciprocity regarding the distance/length!!!

The distances on the one reference frame are just smaller than the other frame!!!

The human B says that on his own reference frame the distance between him and the muon A is 1905 metres, and the muon A says that on its own reference frame the distance between them is 217 metres (**figure 11**)!!!

The human B and the muon A are **not** talking about the distance between them at different moments, but instead they refer to the same moment, because both are talking about the moment when human A & muon A are next to each other and also human B & muon B are next to each other!!!

If the human B and the muon A were talking about the distance between them referring at different moments, then it would be understandable to have different opinions, but both they refer to the same moment which is the moment when human A & muon A are next to each other and also human B & muon B are next to each other!!!

Let's compare how the human A and the muon A see things, according to the scientific community.

What the scientific community actually says that is happening is that when the muon A and the human A are next to each other (**figure 11**), the human A says that on its own reference frame the human B and the muon B are 1905 metres away, but the muon A says that on its own reference frame the human B and the muon B are 217 metres away!!!!

So, why there is no reciprocity regarding the distances/lengths???

There is not reciprocity regarding the distances because when the human A and the muon A are next to each other (figure 11**), the human A says that the human B with the muon B are 1905 metres away from them but the muon A says the they are 217 metres away from them!!!**

Let's analyze it:

Reality for the human A: When the human A and the muon A are next to each other(**figure 11**), the human A says that the human B is stationary meaning he is on the same reference frame, and he is 1905 metres away, and so the muon B which is next to the human B is also 1905 metres away.

Reality for the muon A: When the human A and the muon A are next to each other(**figure 11**), the muon A says that the muon B is stationary meaning it is on the same reference frame, and it is 217 metres away, and so the human B which is next to the muon B is also 217 metres away. Think about it!

For the human A, everything that is next to the human B is at the same distance away from him with the human B, and for the muon A, everything that is next to the muon B is at the same distance away from it with the muon B!!!

If we say that on the reference frame of the muon A the human B is 217 metres away(which is what the scientists are saying), the only reason to say it is because the muon B is 217 metres away and the human B is next to it(**figure 11**)!!!!

It is similar with what the human A says about the human B and the muon B!!!

For the human A, everything that is next to the human B is 1905 metres away!

The muon A must say something similar, meaning that for the muon A, everything that is next to the muon B is at the same distance away with the muon B, and if we say that the human B is 217 metres away this means that the muon B is 217 metres away!!!

So, where is the reciprocity regarding the distances/lengths???

You don't agree that when the muon A is next to the human A according to the muon A the muon B is 217 metres away???

In your opinion which is the distance between the muons A & B on the reference frame of the muons???

When the muon A is next to the human A and "says"(according to the scientific community) that on its own reference frame the human B is 217 metres away, how far away from the muon A is the muon B on the reference frame of the muons???

Let's see something very important.

One may ask:

*How the human B knows when the muon A is next to the human A(**figure 11**)???*

He will use light in order to be informed about the position of the muon A???

The answer is that the human B will not use light!!!

So, how the human B will understand what has happen, and how he will know where and when each muon was???

It is simple! The human B will figure it out later!!!!

It has nothing to do with the information that the human will get using light, meaning that it has nothing to do with the "relativity of simultaneity"!!!!

The human B will figure it out using logic and mathematics!!!

So how it will happen???

*The muon A eventually will be next to the human B(**figure 12**)!!!*

The human B says that he knows the speed of the muons A & B, which is $0.993 c$ or 297.5 metres/microsecond, and he also knows the distance between him and the human A, which is 1905 metres on the reference frame of the humans.

So it is simple for the human B to figure out when the muon A was next the human A, and figure out that the muon A was next to the human A when the muon B was next to the human B!!!

But, when the muon A was where the human B says that it was, meaning when it was next to the human A (**figure 11**), according to the scientific community on the reference frame of the muon A the distance between the muon A and the human B is 217 metres and not 1905 metres which is what the human B says!!!

And the question is:

*How the muon A "knows" where the human B is when muon A and human A are next to each other (**figure 11**)???*

Again, it is simple! The muon A will figure it out later!!!

(If you replace the muon A with a human it will be easier to visualise how the muon A will "figure out" what happens)

As previously mentioned, eventually the human B and the muon A will be next to each other (**figure 12**).

First the human A and the muon A will be next to each other (**figure 11**), and afterwards the human B and the muon A will be next to each other (**figure 12**).

The muons regard themselves as stationary, and according to the muons the humans are the ones that are on the move!!!

The muon A "knows", like the human B knows, which is the relative speed between the muons and the humans, and of course the muon A also knows which are the distances between the muons, like the humans A & B know the distance between them!!!

When the muon A is next to the human B (**figure 12**) according to the muon A the human A is 217 metres away!!!

So, due to the fact that the muon A "knows" the speed of the humans B & A it can figure out where the human B was when the muon A and the human A were next to each other, meaning that the muon A can figure out next to which muon the human B was when the muon A and the human A were next to each other!!!

The muon next to which the human B was, we call it muon B!!!

So, if we say that when the muon A was next to the human A on the reference frame of the muon A the human B is 217 metres away, this means that the muon B is 217 metres away from the muon A on the reference frame of the muons, because the muon A has figure out that the human B was next to the muon B when muon A and human A were next to each other!!!

So, what do we have here???

We have the human B saying that when the muon B was next to him on his own reference frame the muon A was 1905 metres away because it was next to the human A.

But what was the reality for the muon A when it was next to the human A, meaning when it was at the location where the human B says that it was???

The muon A "says" that on its own reference frame, when muon A and human A were next to each other, the human B was 217 metres away because he was next to the muon B!!!

So, both the human B and the muon A are talking about the distance between them, each on its own reference frame, but they disagree on which is that distance!!!

So, there is no reciprocity regarding the distances/lengths!!!!

All there is, is that the distances on the muons frame are smaller!!!

Muon A and human B are talking about the distance between them referring to the same moment because both are talking about the distance between them at the moment when muon A & human A were next to each other and also muon B & human B were next to each other!!!

The muon A "says" to the human B:

When I and the human A were next to each other, you were next to the muon B and so you were 217 metres away from me!!!

The human B says to the muon A:

When I and the muon B were next to each other, you were next to the human A and so you were 1905 away from me!!!

This means that the muon A and the human B disagree about the distance between them referring at the moment when muon A & human A were next to each other and also muon B & human B were next to each other, meaning that they disagree about the distance between them referring to the same moment!!!!

When the muon A was next to the human A the human B says that on its own reference frame the distance between the human B and the muon A is 1905 metres, but when the muon A was at this place that the human B says, the muon A says that on its own reference frame the distance between the human B and the muon A is 217 metres and not 1905 metres!!!

So, the question is which of the two is right???

Why the humans are right and not the muons???

The distances on the muons frame are smaller, but why???

Why it is not happening the opposite meaning why are not smaller the distances on the humans frame???

(If you replace the muon A with a human it will help you visualize the situation.

I've used the terms "says" & "knows" when referring to the muon A, but of course the muon A does not "know" and does not "say" anything.

So, if you replace the muon A with a human it will be easier to visualize.)

Again I have to note that what we have is two inertial reference frames in relative motion, the reference frame of the humans(with the mountain) and the reference frame of the muons **(figure 11)!!!**

The human B says to the muon A:

When you are next to the human A (figure 11) the distance between us is 1905 metres!!!

But the muon A says to the human B:

No, when I am next to the human A (figure 11) the distance between us is 217 metres!!!

Figure 12. The muon A is now next to the human B.

Until now we have used only the [distance/length](#) on our examples, so next let's also use [time](#)!!!

It would be better if you imagine that the muon A is a human because the muon A will have to use a clock and measure time, which of course is something that only a human can do. So, if you imagine that in the place of the muon A there is a human it will be much easier to visualise what is happening!!!

And something important:

The humans and the muons agree on which is the relative speed between them, and they agree that it is $0.993 c$ or 297.5 metres/microsecond.

What the [human B](#) does???

First the [muon B](#) passes next to the [human B](#)(**figure 11**) and afterwards the [muon A](#) passes next to the [human B](#)(**figure 12**).

Suppose that the [human B](#) has a clock and he was watching that clock while the muons were passing next to him.

The human B sees that the muon A passes next to him 6.4 microseconds(μ s) after the muon B, and since he knows the speed of the muons he can figure out that when the muon B was next to him the muon A was next to the human A.

So, we can imagine that the following scenario can happen:

When the muon B is next to the human B(**figure 11**), the human B starts his clock.

When the muon A is next to the human B(**figure 12**), the human B stops his clock and sees that his clock has count 6.4 microseconds(μ s).

The human B knows the distance between him and the human A, and he also knows the relative speed between the muons and the humans, which is $0.993 c$ or 297,5 metres/microsecond, meaning that the human B can figure out that when the muon B was next to him the muon A was next to the human A, meaning that when the human B was starting his clock the muon A was next the human A, because he understands that the muon A needs 6.4 microseconds to travel the 1905 metres from the human A to the human B!!!

So, the human B start his clock when muon A & human A were next to each other and also muon B & human B were next to each other(**figure 11**), and stop his clock when muon A & human B were next to each other(**figure 12**), and his clock counts 6.4 microseconds.

But, what the muon A does???

As we have said earlier, according to the scientific community, when the muon A is next to the human A at the top of the mountain(**figure 11**), on the reference frame of the muon A the human B is 217 metres away.

The scientific community says that while the muon A travels from the human A to the human B, its clock counts 0.73 microseconds(μ s).

Suppose that the muon A has a clock!!!

When muon A and human A are next to each other the muon A start its clock(**figure 11**).

When the muon A and the human B are next to each other(**figure 12**) the muon A stops its clock and "sees" that it has count 0.73 microseconds.

The muon A "knows" which was the distance between the muon B and the muon A, and it also "knows" the relative speed between the humans

and the muons, which is 297.5 metres/microsecond, meaning that the muon A can "figure out" that when the muon A and the human A were next to each other also the human B and the muon B were next to each other, meaning that when the muon A was starting its clock the human B was next to the muon B!!!

The muon A regards itself as stationary, and so according to the muon A the human B is on the move, meaning that the reality for the muon A is that the human B travels the distance of 217 metres, from muon B to muon A, in 0.73 microseconds(μ s)!!!

So, the muon A start its clock when muon A & human A were next to each other and also muon B & human B were next to each other(**figure 11**), which is the same with the human B, and stop its clock when muon A & human B were next to each other(**figure 12**), which is also the same with the human B, and the clock on the muon A counts 0.73 microseconds.

So, both the human B and the muon A start their clocks when muon A & human A were next to each other and also human B & muon B were next to each other(**figure 11**), and stop their clocks when human B and muon A meet(**figure12**), meaning that human B and muon A start their clocks simultaneously and stop their clocks simultaneously, but the clock of the human B counts 6.4 microseconds(μ s) and the clock of the muon A counts 0.73 microseconds(μ s)!!!!!!

So, the time on the muons is slower than the time on the humans and there is no reciprocity!!!!

What we have here is that the time on the muon A is running slower than the time on the human B, and of course the question is why???

Why it is not happening the opposite???

Why it is not slower the time on the human???

What we have is two inertial reference frames in relative motion, the frame of the muons and the frame of the humans, and we say that there is no preferred frame!!!

The human B is on the move on the reference frame of the muons, moving from muon B to muon A, and the muon A is on the move on the reference frame of the humans, moving from human A to human B, but the time on the muon A is running slower than the time on the human B!!!

All that we have is just a case where the time of the muons is slower than the time of the humans with no reciprocal effect!!!

Of course its easy to understand that human B and muon A stop their clocks simultaneously because they stop their clocks when they meet(**figure 12**), but they also start their clocks simultaneously because both start their clocks when human A & muon A are next to each other and also human B & muon B are next to each other(**figure 11**)!!!

We don't use light in order to be informed about the moment of activation of the clocks on the human B and the muon A, meaning that the "relativity of simultaneity" has nothing to do here! The "relativity of simultaneity" has to do with information that we get using light!!!

Here, all we use is our logic and calculations, and using our logic and calculations we conclude about the simultaneous activation of the clocks on the human B and the muon A!!!

The clocks of the human B and the muon A start when the muons and the humans are in specific positions relative to each other, positions which the human B and the muon A agree upon, and which are the positions that we see in the **figure 11**!!!

Human B and muon A stop their clocks when they meet(**figure 12**)!!!

Conclusion:

What we have is motion of the muons on the reference frame of the humans and motion of the humans on the reference frame of the muons, meaning that **we have two reference frames in relative motion with each other, and there is no preferred reference frame!!!**

Human B and muon A agree about the relative speed between them and they say that is 297.5 metres/microsecond.

But, as you can see **there is no reciprocity regarding time and length/distance!!!**

The time and the distance/length on the one reference frame are smaller than the other!!!!

Why this is happening since there is no preferred reference frame???

Why is not happening the opposite???

Something is wrong in the way that the scientific community interprets the findings!!!